

***Cumulative Assessment Group membership
using QSAR information
and
Applications of the TTC concept to impute missing tox data
in EuroMix***

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EuroMix training material
May 2019

Content

- 1. Introduction to EuroMix project**
- 2. Generate information about CAG membership based on QSAR**
- 3. Imputation of TTC values when hazard data is missing**

EuroMix methodology and tools

EuroMix handbook

- Methodology and tools for mixture risk assessment
- Examples

EuroMix toolbox

- Web based toolbox for mixture risk assessment
- Data repository

EuroMix handbook for mixture risk assessment

Johanna Zilliacus, Anna Beronius, Annika Hanberg, Karolinska Institutet, Sweden
Mirjam Luiten and Jacob van Klaveren, RIVM, The Netherlands
Hilko van der Voet, Wageningen University & Research, Biometris, The Netherlands

EuroMix handbook and the EuroMix toolbox provide practical support to apply the recent OECD and EFSA guidance documents in mixture risk assessment

This project is funded by the Horizon 2020 Framework Programme of the European Union

EuroMix toolbox

Web-based toolbox for mixture risk assessment

Based on previous MCRA tool

Upload toxicity and exposure data

Calculate exposure levels, relative potency factors, risk levels

A screenshot of the EuroMix toolbox web interface. At the top is a dark blue navigation bar with icons for user profile, menu, and help. Below the bar is a header image showing a bunch of dark purple grapes. The main content area has a white background with a title "Welcome to MCRA 9 (beta), the EuroMix toolbox" and a subtitle "Chemical exposure, hazard and risk assessment". The text describes the daily exposure to chemical mixtures and the project's goal to develop new testing methods to reduce animal testing.

Welcome to MCRA 9 (beta), the EuroMix toolbox
Chemical exposure, hazard and risk assessment

Every day, we are exposed to a mixture of multiple chemicals via food intake, inhalation and dermal contact. The risk to health that may result from this depends on how the effects of different chemicals in the mixture combine, and whether there is any synergism or antagonism between them. The number of different combinations of chemicals in mixtures is infinite and an efficient test strategy for mixtures is lacking. Furthermore, there is a societal need to reduce animal testing, which is the current practice in safety testing of chemicals.

The EuroMix project will deliver a mixture test strategy and test instruments using novel techniques as recently proposed by the Joint Research Centre (JRC) of the European Commission. The tests will result in data needed for refining future risk assessment of mixtures relevant to national food safety authorities, public health institutes, the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA), the European Chemical Agency (ECHA), industry, regulatory bodies and other stakeholders. Ultimately, this will provide information for future risk management decisions on the safety of chemicals in mixtures to be taken by the European Commission and the Codex Alimentarius.

EuroMix toolbox user manual

Web-based user manual

- Descriptions of each module
- Settings
- Data formats

A screenshot of the MCRA Documentation web page. The page has a dark blue header with "MCRA Documentation" and a search bar. A dark sidebar on the left lists the contents. The main content area shows the breadcrumb "Docs » MCRA documentation", the title "MCRA documentation", a welcome message, and a detailed "Contents:" list with sub-items.

MCRA Documentation

Search docs

CONTENTS:

- Colophon
- Introduction
- About the toolbox
- Modules
- Examples
- References
- Appendix

Docs » MCRA documentation

MCRA documentation

Welcome to the MCRA 9 documentation.

Contents:

- Colophon
 - Contributors to MCRA
- Introduction
- About the toolbox
 - Modular design
 - Toolbox data repository
 - Workspaces and actions
- Modules
 - Primary entity modules
 - Consumption modules
 - Occurrence modules
 - Exposure modules
 - Hazard modules
 - In-silico modules
 - Kinetic modules
 - Risk modules
- Examples
- References
- Appendix
 - Munro collection
 - Unit definitions
 - Transformations
 - Gauss-Hermite
 - Concentration models
 - Chronic exposure assessment, daily consumed foods
 - Chronic exposure assessment, episodically consumed foods
 - Unit variability
 - Screening calculation for large Cumulative Assessment Groups
 - Uncertainty analysis

EuroMix methodology and tools for mixture risk assessment

- Component-based approach
- Grouping based on toxicological considerations
- Dose addition as default model
- Relative potency factors (RPF) approach
- Probabilistic exposure assessment
- Mainly dietary exposure

Very flexible

- Also applicable for other grouping principles (structure, exposure...)
- Any type of substance
- RPFs based on ADI/TDI, NOAEL/BMD for critical or specific effect or same potency for all substances
- Methodology to handle data poor substances

Content

1. Introduction to EuroMix project
2. **Generate information about CAG membership based on QSAR**
3. Imputation of TTC values when hazard data is missing

What are (Q)SARs?

SAR: alerts

QSAR: quantitative models (within an alert, or "global")

(Q)SARs

chemical structure and/or physico-chemical property
X

Biological (effect) property
Y

- Solubility
- Log Kow
- Electronegativity
- E_{homo} / E_{lumo}
- E-states
- Topological indices

- no-effect concentrations
- bioaccumulation
- LC50
- Mutagenicity
- Liver toxicity

Quantitative model relating Y to X (QSAR): $Y = f(X)$
 Qualitative model relating Y to X (SAR): if (property) then (effect)

prediction of fate or effect properties for related chemicals

Steatosis AOP network

Green = predicted *in silico*,
measured *in vitro*
Purple = predicted *in silico*,
measured *in vivo*
Orange = measured *in vitro*
and *in vivo*
Blue = not measured

QSARs and grouping principles

EuroMix

European Test and Risk Assessment Strategies for Mixtures

Project number 633172

Collaborative project
H2020-SFS-2014-2

Deliverable D2.2 – Report

Report on the use of *in-silico* methods for the prioritisation of substances and mixtures thereof

This project is funded by the Horizon
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European Union

QSARs to predict Liver Toxicity

List of relevant models for Liver Tox in Euromix: CAG level

- **DEREK Hepatotoxicity Alert Score** - level 1 (2)
- MULTICASE Consensus Highest - level 1
- Pizzo Alert Score - level 1
- **COSMOS Nuclear Receptor model** - level 4
- PADEL Predict Hepatotoxic - level 1
- Toolbox rep.dose HESS alerts; Hepatotox - level 1
- Fera C4.5 model CDK descriptors - level 1
- **OCHEM AhR activity** - level 4
- **OCHEM PPARg activity** - level 4

- **FERA dedicated QSAR model Steatosis** - level 2

Liver Toxicity – DEREK

Deltamethrin – CAG liver toxicity

- Alert-617: Halogenated Hydrocarbon
- These compounds may cause steatosis and/or necrosis

The screenshot displays the DEREK software interface. The main window shows the chemical structure of Deltamethrin, a pyrethroid insecticide, with a cyanide group and a brominated side chain highlighted. The interface includes a menu bar (File, Window, Prediction, Reports, Tools, Help), a toolbar, and a sidebar with navigation options like 'Study Folder', 'Structure', 'Alerts P', 'Derek P', 'Structure-3', 'Derek P', 'Structure-4', and 'Derek P'. The 'Alert Details' panel on the right provides a description of the alert, a chemical structure diagram with substituents R1-R6, and a list of comments explaining the hepatotoxicity of halogenated aliphatic hydrocarbons. The 'Prediction Navigator' at the bottom left shows a list of predictions, with 'Alert - 617: Halogenated hydrocarbon' highlighted as 'PLAUSIBLE'.

Alert Details

Description Image

R1-R2

R5 R4
R6 R3

R1 = Cl, Br, I
R2 = alkyl group with less than 5 carbon atoms
R3 = F, Cl, Br, I
R4-R6 = C, H, F, Cl, Br, I
Halothane or analogues are excluded

Comments

This alert describes the hepatotoxicity of halogenated aliphatic hydrocarbons. These compounds may cause necrosis and/or steatosis, and liver tumours in humans and experimental animals.

Haloaliphatic hydrocarbons have been extensively used in the chemical and agricultural industry, in medicine, and domestically as solvents and chemical reagents [Zimmerman].

These compounds are known occupational and environmental toxicants. Many of them are thought to possess a potential for causing liver damage [Zimmerman]. Acute hepatic injury in the form of centrilobular necrosis and macrovacuolar steatosis has been reported with the most toxic agents. Typical examples include carbon tetrachloride, widely employed as an experimental model for the study of certain hepatotoxic effects, chloroform, formerly used as an anaesthetic agent, tetrachloroethane, vinyl chloride and tetrachloroethylene. Chronic injury characterised by cirrhosis and/or hepatic carcinoma has also been described with the cited agents [Zimmerman].

Validation Comments

Prediction Navigator

Show predictions of at least: EQUIVOCAL

Derek KB 2014 1.0 [Certified by: Lhasa Limited, Leeds, Yorkshire, UK]

- Cyanide-type effects
- Hepatotoxicity
- mammal - PLAUSIBLE
- Alert - 617: Halogenated hydrocarbon
- Mitochondrial dysfunction
- Mutagenicity in vitro
- Neurotoxicity

Nuclear Receptor Models: ochem.eu

Deltamethrin:

AhR model:

INACTIVE
(88% accuracy)

PPARg model:

ACTIVE
(84% accuracy)

In EuroMix Molecular Docking models for 16 Liver Nuclear Receptors have been developed, giving estimated receptor binding energies.

Content

- 1. How to organize data needed to perform hazard assessment :**
 - CAG membership and datafiles used in the exercise**
- 2. Exercise: Apply the FERA QSAR prediction for CAG membership in the dietary exposure calculations and compare the MoE results with the first (dietary exposure) exercise.**

Secondary input data exposure.mdb

Table Tools Secondary input data exposure : Database (Access 20...)

File Home Create External Data Database Tools Fields Table

View Paste Copy Cut Format Painter Filter Sort & Filter Records Find Text Formatting

All Access Objects Search... Tables AssessmentGroupMembershipModels AssessmentGroupMemberships Effect Food FoodProperties FoodTranslation HazardDoses Populations Processingfactor ProcessingType Substances VariabilityFactor

idGroupMembershipModel	idSubstance	GroupMemberShip
Steatosis-liver	RF-0005-001-PPP	1
Steatosis-liver	RF-0006-001-PPP	1
Steatosis-liver	RF-0007-001-PPP	1
Steatosis-liver	RF-0011-001-PPP	1
Steatosis-liver	RF-0013-001-PPP	1
Steatosis-liver	RF-0014-001-PPP	1
Steatosis-liver	RF-0112-001-PPP	1
Steatosis-liver	RF-0470-001-PPP	1
Steatosis-liver	RF-0025-001-PPP	1
Steatosis-liver	RF-0030-001-PPP	1
Steatosis-liver	RF-0038-001-PPP	1
Steatosis-liver	RF-0039-001-PPP	1
Steatosis-liver	RF-00003374-PAR	1
Steatosis-liver	RF-0493-001-PPP	1
Steatosis-liver	RF-0042-001-PPP	1
Steatosis-liver	RF-0043-001-PPP	1
Steatosis-liver	RF-00003033-PAR	1
Steatosis-liver	RF-0048-001-PPP	1
Steatosis-liver	RF-1056-001-PPP	1
Steatosis-liver	RF-0052-001-PPP	1
Steatosis-liver	RF-00003327-PAR	1
Steatosis-liver	RF-0053-002-PPP	1
Steatosis-liver	RF-0055-001-PPP	1
Steatosis-liver	RF-0061-001-PPP	1
Steatosis-liver	RF-0041-001-PPP	1
Steatosis-liver	RF-0064-001-PPP	1
Steatosis-liver	RF-0080-001-PPP	1
Steatosis-liver	RF-0084-001-PPP	1
Steatosis-liver	RF-0092-001-PPP	1
Steatosis-liver	RF-0098-001-PPP	1
Steatosis-liver	RF-0101-001-PPP	1

Record: 1 of 144 No Filter Search

This project is funded by the Horizon 2020 Framework Programme of the European Union

QSAR data – model description

Active substances QSAR steatosis flusilazole in.xlsx

active substances QSAR steatosis.xlsx - Microsoft Excel

File Home Insert Page Layout Formulas Data Review View Developer Add-Ins Places IBM Connections Acrobat ?

Clipboard Font Alignment Number Styles Cells Editing

E49 fx

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J
1	id	Name	Description	idEffect	Accuracy	Sensitivity	Specificity	Reference		
2	QSAR-FERA-Steatosis	QSAR-FERA-Steatosis	QSAR-FERA-Steatosis	Steatosis-liver	0.75	0.74	0.76	JV Cotterill et al. in preparation.		
3										
4										
5										
6										
7										
8										
9										
10										
11										
12										
13										
14										
15										

QsarMembershipModels QsarMemberships

Ready 100%

QSAR Data – Prediction results.

Active substances QSAR steatosis flusilazole in.xlsx

active substances QSAR steatosis.xlsx - Microsoft Excel

File Home Insert Page Layout Formulas Data Review View Developer Add-Ins Places IBM Connections Acrobat

Clipboard Font Alignment Number Styles Cells Editing

A1 fx idQSARMembershipModel

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K
1	idQSARMembershipModel	idSubstance	MembershipScore								
2	QSAR-FERA-Steatosis	RF-0005-001-PPP	0								
3	QSAR-FERA-Steatosis	RF-0006-001-PPP	0								
4	QSAR-FERA-Steatosis	RF-0007-001-PPP	0								
5	QSAR-FERA-Steatosis	RF-0011-001-PPP	1								
6	QSAR-FERA-Steatosis	RF-0013-001-PPP	1								
7	QSAR-FERA-Steatosis	RF-0014-001-PPP	0								
8	QSAR-FERA-Steatosis	RF-0112-001-PPP	1								
9	QSAR-FERA-Steatosis	RF-0470-001-PPP	0								
10	QSAR-FERA-Steatosis	RF-0025-001-PPP	0								
11	QSAR-FERA-Steatosis	RF-0030-001-PPP	0								
12	QSAR-FERA-Steatosis	RF-0038-001-PPP	1								
13	QSAR-FERA-Steatosis	RF-0039-001-PPP	1								
14	QSAR-FERA-Steatosis	RF-00003374-PAR	1								
15	QSAR-FERA-Steatosis	RF-0493-001-PPP	0								
16	QSAR-FERA-Steatosis	RF-0042-001-PPP	0								
17	QSAR-FERA-Steatosis	RF-0043-001-PPP	1								
18	QSAR-FERA-Steatosis	RF-00003033-PAR	1								
19	QSAR-FERA-Steatosis	RF-0048-001-PPP	1								
20	QSAR-FERA-Steatosis	RF-1056-001-PPP	1								

Ready | 100%

QSAR data – model description

Active substances QSAR based (all).xlsx

	A	B	C	D	E
1	id	CodeSystem	Name	Description	idEffect
2	QSAR-DEREK-Hepatotoxicity	EuroMix	QSAR-DEREK-Hepatotoxicity	DEREK Hepatotoxicity Alert Score - subset is used to predict steatosis	Hepatotoxicity
3	QSAR-MCASE-Hepatotoxicity	EuroMix	QSAR-MCASE-Hepatotoxicity	Multicase CONSENSUS_Highest Score (No Call classed Positive	Hepatotoxicity
4	QSAR-PizzoAlert-Hepatotoxicity	EuroMix	QSAR-PizzoAlert-Hepatotoxicity	Pizzo Alert Score	Hepatotoxicity
5	QSAR-COSMOS-NR-Hepatotoxicity	EuroMix	QSAR-COSMOS-NR-Hepatotoxicity	COSMOS Nuclear Receptor model for Steatosis liver nuclear receptors used to predict	Steatosis-liver
6	QSAR-FERA-Pizzo-Hepatotoxicity	EuroMix	QSAR-FERA-Pizzo-Hepatotoxicity	FERA rebuilt model using the Pizzo dataset	Hepatotoxicity
7	QSAR-PADEL-predict-Hepatotoxicity	EuroMix	QSAR-PADEL-predict-Hepatotoxicity	PADEL model Predicting Hepatotoxicity	Hepatotoxicity
8	QSAR-Toolbox-HESS-Hepatotoxicity	EuroMix	QSAR-Toolbox-HESS-Hepatotoxicity	Toolbox repeated dose HESS alert specific for Hepatotoxicity	Hepatotoxicity
9	QSAR-OCHEM-AhR-Hepatotoxicity	EuroMix	QSAR-OCHEM-AhR-Hepatotoxicity	OCHEM AhR receptor binding model used to predict hepatotoxicity - and to predict s	AhR-act-liver
10	QSAR-OCHEM-PPARgamma-Hepatotoxicity	EuroMix	QSAR-OCHEM-PPARgamma-Hepatotoxicity	OCHEM PPARg receptor binding model used to predict hepatotoxicity - and to predict s	PPARgamma-act-liver
11	QSAR-DOCKING-Steatosis-receptors	EuroMix	QSAR-DOCKING-Steatosis-receptors	at least one of the 16 Liver NR Docking models from UniMilano above binding thresh	Steatosis-liver
12	QSAR-FERA-Steatosis	EuroMix	QSAR-FERA-Steatosis	FERA developed model using the reference dataset for Steatosis - to predict steatosis	Steatosis-liver
13	QSAR-VEGA-CAESAR-Developmental-toxic	EuroMix	QSAR-VEGA-CAESAR-developmental-toxic	VEGA CAESAR model	Developmental-toxicity
14	QSAR-VEGA-PG-Developmental-toxicity	EuroMix	QSAR-VEGA-PG-developmental-toxicity	VEGA PG model	Developmental-toxicity
15	QSAR-DEREK-Developmental-toxicity	EuroMix	QSAR-DEREK-Developmental-toxicity	DEREK alert for Develoemental toxicity	Developmental-toxicity
16	QSAR-TEST-Developmental-toxicity	EuroMix	QSAR-TEST-Developmental-toxicity	USEPA TEST Dev Tox model Consensus	Developmental-toxicity
17	QSAR-DEREK-Estrogen	EuroMix	QSAR-DEREK-Estrogen	DEREK Score (ER or Oestrogenicity alerts)	ER-agonism
18	QSAR-OECD-toolbox-ER	EuroMix	QSAR-OECD-toolbox-ER	OECD Toolbox Estrogen Receptor Binding model	ER-agonism
19	QSAR-OECD-toolbox-rTER-expert-system	EuroMix	QSAR-OECD-toolbox-rTER-expert-system	OECD Toolbox rTER Expert System	ER-agonism
20	QSAR-OECD-toolbox-DART-ER-AR	EuroMix	QSAR-OECD-toolbox-DART-ER-AR	OECD Toolbox DART alert specific for ER / AR pathway	ER-agonism
21	QSAR-VEGA-RBA	EuroMix	QSAR-VEGA-RBA	VEGA RBA Model	ER-agonism
22	QSAR-COSMOS-ER	EuroMix	QSAR-COSMOS-ER	COSMOS Nuclear Receptor model: ER	ER-agonism
23	QSAR-OCHEM-ER	EuroMix	QSAR-OCHEM-ER	OCHEM ER Model 1 estrogen receptor alpha agonists qualit	ER-agonism
24	QSAR-VEGA-CERAPP	EuroMix	QSAR-VEGA-CERAPP	VEGA CERAPP SCORE	ER-agonism
25	QSAR-DOCKING-ER-binding	EuroMix	QSAR-DOCKING-ER-binding	at least one of the ER docking models from UniMilano above binding threshold energ	ER-agonism
26	QSAR-COSMOS-AR	EuroMix	QSAR-COSMOS-AR	COSMOS Nuclear Receptor model: AR	AR-antagonism
27	QSAR-OCHEM-AR-model1	EuroMix	QSAR-OCHEM-AR-model1	OCHEM AR Model 1 androgen agonists MDA qualitative	AR-antagonism
28	QSAR-OCHEM-AR-model2	EuroMix	QSAR-OCHEM-AR-model2	OCHEM AR Model 2 androgen receptor agonists qualitative	AR-antagonism
29	QSAR-OCHEM-AR-model3	EuroMix	QSAR-OCHEM-AR-model3	OCHEM AR Model 3 (log RP AR)	AR-antagonism
30	QSAR-OCHEM-aromatase	EuroMix	QSAR-OCHEM-aromatase	OCHEM Aromatase inhibitors qualitative	Steroidogenesis-altered
31					
32					

Exercise QSAR and assessment group membership EuroMix

You have performed a calculation following the EFSA guidance on the use of probabilistic modelling for modelling dietary exposure to pesticides using an optimistic calculation scenario.

The inclusion of all 144 substances in the CAG steatosis is still discussed and very uncertain. Not all substances are considered to be fully dose additive for the effect of Liver Steatosis. QSAR might help to refine which chemicals should be grouped in the CAG and which can be left out of the dietary exposure calculations.

We will go back to the “Dietary exposure” action and change the settings under Data / Active substances in order to only include those substances that are predicted by the FERA QSAR to cause steatosis, and rerun the risk calculation.

How is the Margin of Exposure going to change?

Change settings

1. Go to the Actions overview by clicking the action icon
2. A **does not necessarily mean** all settings are the way you want. We want to change the settings determining which substances are members of the CAG (active substances).
3. Go to active substances, this is where we determine which substances are "active" in the risk calculation.

Dietary exposures

a405ce7d

Scope

(optional) Populations (15 in scope)

Foods (3278 in scope) | Processing types (32 in scope)

Substances (144 in scope)

Effects (1 in scope)

Inputs

Consumptions per food as measured

Concentration models

Processing factors

Active substances (optional) (1 assessment group membership models selected)

Relative potency factors

Change settings

1. Click on derive membership from QSAR membership data

Dietary exposures / Active substances

ce853346

Scope

Effects (1 in scope)

Substances (144 in scope)

Active substances

Use data

Compute

Assessment group membership settings

Save Changes

Restrict to substances with available hazard doses

Derive memberships from molecular docking data

Derive memberships from QSAR membership data

Use probabilistic assessment group memberships

Change settings

1. Save settings

Dietary exposures / Active substances ce853346

Scope

Effects (1 in scope) ✓

Substances (144 in scope) ✓

Active substances

Use data Compute

Assessment group membership settings

Restrict to substances with available hazard doses

Derive memberships from molecular docking data

Derive memberships from QSAR membership data

...

Save Changes

Change data and settings

1. Insert inputs for QSAR membership

Dietary exposures / Active substances 4a93f9aa

Scope

Effects (1 in scope) ✓

Substances (144 in scope) ✓

Inputs

QSAR membership models

Active substances

Use data Compute

Assessment group membership settings

Restrict to substances with available hazard doses

Derive memberships from molecular docking data

Derive memberships from QSAR membership data

Use probabilistic assessment group memberships

Change settings

1. Insert QSAR membership models data source
2. Browse to data source

Dietary exposures / Active substances / QSAR membership models

d06724b0

Scope

Substances (144 in scope)

Effects (1 in scope)

QSAR membership models data source

Not specified

active substances QSAR steatosis flusalis...

 Browse

 Clear

Select input data for QSAR

1. Select EuroMix training
2. A new window pops-up.
3. Select *'active substance QSAR steatosis flusilazole in.xlsx'*

Browse datasources

≡ Data

Name ▾

 EuroMix Training

 EuromixTraining01

Browse datasources

≡ Data / EuroMixTraining

Name ▾

↑ (Data)

 active substances QSAR steatosis flusilazole in.xlsx

Select the file

1. Select the file

Browse datasources

☰ Data / EuroMixTraining

Name ▾

Version

Date

↑ (Data)

📄 active substances QSAR steatosis flusalisole in.xlsx

1

10-02-2019 20:06

Selected: active substances QSAR steatosis flusalisole in.xlsx

Data groups: Toggle single Toggle all

QSAR membership models

Select

Cancel

This project is funded by the Horizon 2020 Framework Programme of the European Union

Summary overview

1. Go to summary overview

Dietary exposures training
Dietary exposures action

Dietary exposures / Active substances / QSAR membership models d06724b0

Scope

- Substances (144 in scope) ✓
- Effects (1 in scope) ✓

QSAR membership models data source

- > active substances QSAR steatosis flusalisole in.xlsx v1 ✓

QSAR membership models data selection

- QSAR membership models: 1 selected

Summary overview

1. Check the scope, settings and data in the assessment (scroll down)
2. Run the simulation

Summary

Scope

Effects	Secondary input data exposure.mdb v1
Foods	Secondary input data exposure.mdb v1
Populations	Secondary input data exposure.mdb v1
Substances	Secondary input data exposure.mdb v1

Settings

Exposure type	Chronic
Dietary exposure calculation tier	EFSA Guidance Optimistic
Apply processing factors	Yes
Processing factor model	Fixed
Apply exposure screening	No
Report consumptions and exposures per individual instead of per kg body weight	No
Covariate modelling	No
Model type	Observed Individual Means

Data

Run the simulation

1. After you start running the simulation, you see a screen with waiting for activation. This takes 10-20 seconds
2. Then waiting for activation changes into running (second screenshot)
3. This might take 2-3 minutes for this exercise. If it takes longer than 10 minutes abort the job

The image displays two screenshots of a web application interface for "Dietary exposures training".

The top screenshot shows the "Results" section with a table containing one entry:

Output	Status	Message	Date	Running time
<input type="checkbox"/> Dietary exposures training	Waiting for activation	Job scheduled for execution (waiting for available resources)...	-	-

The bottom screenshot shows the same interface after the simulation has progressed:

Output	Status	Message	Date	Running time
<input type="checkbox"/> Dietary exposures training	Running	Conversion finished	-	-

View the output

1. Go to dietary sub-action results
2. Open active substances
3. Look at the numbers of chemicals with positive and negative assessment group memberships from the QSAR

Results / EFSA optimistic QSAR

Action settings **Sub-action results** Dietary exposures

- > Substances
- > Effects
- > Consumptions
- > Points of departure
- > QSAR membership models
- ✓ Active substances

Assessment group memberships

View the output

1. Go to dietary exposure
2. Open observed individual means
3. Open percentiles
4. Look at the Margin of Exposure at different percentile

Results / EFSA optimistic QSAR

Action settings

Sub-action results

Dietary exposures

> Dietary exposure distribution (daily intakes)

> Exposures by food

> Exposures by substance

> Exposures by food and substance

✓ **Observed individual means**

> Graph total

> Graph upper tail

✓ **Percentiles**

Reference: Fusilazole, PoD = 530 µg/kg bw/day

Mean exposure: 0,263 (µg/kg bw/day)

Percentage	Exposure (µg/kg bw/day)	Percentage of PoD (%)	Margin of exposure
50.00	0.09316	0.02	5689
90.00	0.7395	0.14	716.7
95.00	1.051	0.20	504.1
99.00	1.87	0.35	283.4
99.90	3.023	0.57	175.3
99.99	4.287	0.83	120.8

View the output

1. Go to Sub-action results
2. Open Active substances, Substance memberships table
3. Look at which substances are in the CAG and which are not. Where is Imazalil?

The screenshot shows the 'Sub-action results' tab selected in the 'Dietary exposures' action. Below the tab, a table displays the results for the 'AG Steatosis-liver' CAG. The table has the following data:

Code assessment group	CAG name	Effect code	Effect name	Number of computed membership scores	Number of certain memberships	Fraction certain membership
AG-Steatosis-liver	AG Steatosis-liver	Steatosis-liver	Steatosis-liver	144	92	0.639

Below this table, the 'Substance memberships table' is expanded, showing a list of substances and their membership scores:

Substance name	Substance code	Membership score
Abamectin (RD)	RF-0011-001-PPP	1
Acequinocyl	RF-0013-001-PPP	1
Benalaxyl (RD)	RF-0038-001-PPP	1
Benfluralin	RF-0039-001-PPP	1
Benthiavallcarb (RD)	RF-0043-001-PPP	1
Bifenazate (sum of bifenazate plus bifenazate-diazene expressed as bifenazate)	RF-00003033-PAR	1
Bitertanol	RF-0048-001-PPP	1
Bixafen	RF-1056-001-PPP	1
Bromopropylate	RF-0052-001-PPP	1

Results overview

Calculation method	Margin of Exposure		
	EFSA pessimistic	EFSA optimistic	EFSA optimistic
substance in scope (CAG)	144	144	92
number of imputations			
Percentile			
50	51.09	4242	5689
90	21.05	681.5	716.7
95	17.12	487.5	504.1
99	11.54	277	283.4
99.9	6.202	173.3	175.3
99.99	5.315	119.8	120.8

All examples are illustrations of how the data from the EuroMix test strategy can be used in future mixture risk assessment. The exercises should not be seen as a real risk assessment.

Probabilistic QSAR memberships

We used one QSAR to assign 0 or 1 probability of CAG membership. But QSAR predictions are not 100% certain, which is reflected in the prediction statistics for each model.

The screenshot shows a Microsoft Excel spreadsheet titled "active substances QSAR steatosis.xlsx". The spreadsheet contains a table with the following data:

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J
1	id	Name	Description	idEffect	Accuracy	Sensitivity	Specificity	Reference		
2	QSAR-FERA-Steatosis	QSAR-FERA-Steatosis	QSAR-FERA-Steatosis	Steatosis-liver	0.75	0.74	0.76	JV Cotterill et al. in preparation.		
3										
4										

This information can be used by the EuroMix software tool to generate probabilistic CAG memberships (also allowing to use multiple QSARs for one CAG membership prediction), to allow for a probabilistic risk assessment.

From the results screen go directly back to the Action settings, by clicking on the Action settings button

MCRA 9 - EuroMix toolbox / CAG membership QSA...
Exposure, Hazard & Risk Assessment workspace

Active substances QSAR
Active substances action

Active substances / Results / Active substances QSAR (2)

Action settings Sub-action results Active substances

Active substances

Assessment group memberships

Membership	Number of substances
Positive membership	92
Negative membership	52

Code assessment group	CAG name	Effect code	Effect name	Number of computed membership scores	Number of certain memberships	Fraction certain membership
AG-Steatosis-liver	AG Steatosis-liver	Steatosis-liver	Steatosis-liver	144	92	0.639

Substance name Substance code Membership score

MCRA 9 - EuroMix toolbox / CAG membership QSA...
Exposure, Hazard & Risk Assessment workspace

EmielRorije

Active substances QSAR
Active substances action

Active substances 5cf71411

Effects (1 in scope) ✓
Substances (144 in scope) ✓

Inputs

Points of departure ✓
QSAR membership models (1 qsar membership models selected) ✓

Active substances

Use data Compute

Assessment group membership settings

Save Changes

Restrict to substances with available hazard doses
 Derive memberships from molecular docking data
 Derive memberships from QSAR membership data
 Use probabilistic assessment group memberships

Membership calculation method
Bayesian (probabilistic)

Default/prior membership probability
0.5

In the Action settings,
Select 'Use probabilistic
assessment group
memberships'

Select 'Bayesian
(probabilistic)' as the
Membership
calculations method.

And set the
Default/prior
membership
probability to 0.5

Save Changes.

Run the action

Goto the Results

Select Active Substances

All substances are now Member of the CAG (144), but 92 have probability 0.755 of being CAG member, and 52 have a probability of 0.255 of being a CAG member Steatosis. Scroll down to see the individual substance results.

The screenshot shows the 'Active substances' results page in the EuroMix application. The page title is 'Active substances / Results / Active substances QSAR (6)'. The 'Active substances' tab is selected and circled in red. Below the tab, there is a bar chart titled 'Assessment group memberships distribution' showing the frequency of substances based on their computed membership probability. The x-axis is 'Computed membership probability' (0 to 1) and the y-axis is 'frequency' (0 to 100). There are two bars: one at approximately 0.255 with a frequency of 52, and another at 0.755 with a frequency of 92. Below the chart is a table with the following data:

Code assessment group	CAG name	Effect code	Effect name	Number of computed membership scores	Number of possible memberships	Number of certain memberships	Mean of computed membership scores	Median of computed membership scores	Fraction possible membership	Fraction certain membership
AG-Steatosis-liver	AG-Steatosis-liver	Steatosis-liver	Steatosis-liver	144	144	0	0.574	0.755	1	0

Application of QSAR results to other substances/ CAGs

In the EuroMix Toolbox an Inventory of food/feed relevant substances is available, in total ~1600 substances:

- PPP (the 144 steatosis dataset is a subset of the PPP substances)
- Biocides
- Food additives
- Environmental contaminants
- Food contact materials
- Mycotoxins
- Other/Pharmaceuticals
-

Results for in total 29 QSAR models and Binding energies from 21 receptor docking models for the 3 endpoints evaluated in EuroMix are provided in the Toolbox:

- Liver toxicity / steatosis
- Developmental toxicity / craniofacial malformations
- Endocrine disruption / Estrogen and Androgen receptor mediated.

Example: Mycotoxins (20) CAG Steatosis

izon
the

Content

1. Introduction to EuroMix project
2. Generate information about CAG membership based on QSAR
3. **Imputation of TTC values when hazard data is missing**

What is TTC?

50th percentile: any chemical in class X has a 50/50 chance of being toxic at a lower concentration

20th percentile: any random chemical in class X has only a 1 in 5 chance of being toxic at a lower concentration

Figure 1. Empirical cumulative distributions of NOELs of compounds in the reference database and log normally fitted cumulative distributions (solid lines). Compounds have been grouped into the structural classes I, II, and III of Cramer et al. (1978).

TTC concept

Fifth percentile NOELs and human exposure thresholds for Cramer et al. (1978) structural classes in the Munro database

Cramer Class	nr. subst.	5th Percentile NOELs, ($\mu\text{g}/\text{kg bw}/\text{day}$)	Human Exposure Threshold = TTC ($\mu\text{g}/\text{day}$) ^a
I	137	2993	1800
II	28	906	540
III	447	147	90
All	612	200	(not used)

a The human exposure threshold was calculated by multiplying the 5th percentile NOEL by 60 (assuming an individual weighs 60 kg) and dividing by a safety factor of 100.

- **The 5th percentile NOELs are used in EuroMix Toolbox as a worst case NOAEL estimate as Point of Departure. In the software tool this option for imputation of missing values is called**
- ***‘Munro P5 (unbiased for uncertainty runs)’***

TTC concept – CAG specific

Fifth percentile NOELs and human exposure thresholds for Cramer et al. (1978) structural classes in the Munro database

Cramer Class	nr. subst.	5th Percentile NOELs, (µg/kg bw/day)	Human Exposure Threshold (µg/day) ^a
I	137	2993	1800
II	28	906	540
III	447	147	90
All	612	200	(not used)

a The human exposure threshold was calculated by multiplying the 5th percentile NOEL by 60 (assuming an individual weighs 60 kg) and dividing by a safety factor of 100.

- **The Munro NOELs are taking into account all possible tox effect, at chronic exposure. But for EuroMix ideally a CAG-specific TTC would be available. This is implemented as:**

- **46 ‘Hazard doses P5 (unbiased for uncertainty runs)’**

This project is funded by the Horizon 2020 Framework Programme of the European Union

Steatosis TTC based NOAELs

Munro TTC based NOAEL (5th %):
0.15 mg/kg bw/day

Steatosis TTC based NOAEL (5th %):
0.50 mg/kg bw/day

**A factor of 3.33
less conservative**

Imputation (TTC based) of missing hazard data

- In case no toxicity data is available from in vitro or in vivo studies it is possible to impute “conservative” NOAEL values. The concept of the Toxicological Threshold of Concern can be used to come up with “safe” NOAEL estimates.
- TTC is based on a database of NOAEL values (all effects) compiled by Munro et al 1996. This database is implemented in the Euromix Toolbox
- Substances can be divided into toxicity classes: the Cramer Classes. These have their own NOAEL distributions and TTC value linked to them.
- The 5th percentile of the NOAEL distributions in each class can be calculated and used as a conservative estimate of NOAEL for substances without any toxicity data

Exercise Dietary Exposure with missing hazard dose and imputation TTC

1. You are going to continue working with the CAG of 144 steatosis substances, but now with *in vivo* PoD data available **for only 45 of these**. It means that for 99 substances in the CAG there is no hazard data (but we do have exposure data!) You might wish to impute missing hazard data based on conservative TTC values, instead of not taking into account these substances in the risk calculations.

2. You are probably still in the results screen

Results

Output	Status	Message	Date	Running time
<input type="checkbox"/> Dietary exposure	Run to completion		10-02-2019 10:04	00:02:18

3. Go back to the summary in the Action Dietary Exposure, and scroll

Results

Output	Status	Message	Date	Running time
<input type="checkbox"/> Dietary exposure	Run to completion		10-02-2019 10:04	00:02:18

Change settings

1. All **does not mean** that all settings are correct for your purposes.
2. Go to Active substances (optional)

The screenshot shows the MCRA 9 web application interface. The browser address bar displays the URL: <https://mcra-test.rivm.nl/EuroMix/WebApp/#/actions/813/DietaryExposures>. The page title is "Dietary exposures" and the user is logged in as "EmielRorije". The main content area is titled "Dietary exposures" and shows a list of settings, each with a green checkmark indicating it is active or correct. The settings are organized into two sections: "Scope" and "Inputs".

Section	Setting	Status
Scope	(optional) Populations (15 in scope)	✓
	Foods (3278 in scope) Processing types (32 in scope)	✓
	Substances (144 in scope)	✓
	Effects (1 in scope)	✓
Inputs	Consumptions per food as measured	✓
	Concentration models	✓
	Processing factors	✓
	Active substances (optional)	✓
	Relative potency factors	✓

At the bottom of the page, there is a "Dietary exposure settings" section and a "Save Changes" button.

Change settings

1. Make sure to DESELECT the option "restrict to substances with available points of departure"

The screenshot shows the MCRA 9 web application interface. The browser address bar displays the URL: `https://mcra-test.rivm.nl/EuroMix/WebApp/#/actions/813/DietaryExposures/AssessmentGroupMemberships`. The page title is "MCRA 9 - EuroMix toolbox / Dietary exposure T... / Dietary exposures". The user is logged in as "EmielRorije". The main content area is titled "Dietary exposures / Active substances" with the ID "6c1e377a".

The "Active substances settings" section is visible, containing the following options:

- Restrict to substances with available points of departure
- Derive memberships from molecular docking data
- Derive memberships from QSAR membership data

A "Save Changes" button is located at the bottom right of the settings section.

Change settings

1. Deselect and make sure to "Save Changes"

The screenshot shows the 'Dietary exposures' interface in the EuroMix toolbox. The 'Active substances settings' section is visible, containing the following options:

- Restrict to substances with available points of departure
- Derive memberships from molecular docking data
- Derive memberships from QSAR membership data

A red circle highlights the first checkbox. A 'Save Changes' button is located to the right of the settings. The interface also shows a 'Scope' section with 'Effects (1 in scope)' and 'Substances (144 in scope)', and an 'Inputs' section with 'Points of departure'. The 'Active substances' section has 'Use data' and 'Compute' buttons.

Impute missing hazard data

1. Go back to Settings again
2. All **does not mean** that all your settings are the way we want.
3. Go to relative potency factors

The screenshot shows the MCRA 9 web application interface. The browser address bar displays the URL: <https://mcra-test.rivm.nl/EuroMix/WebApp/#/actions/813/DietaryExposures>. The page title is "MCRA 9 - EuroMix toolbox / Dietary exposure T... / Dietary exposures". The user is logged in as "EmielRorije". The main content area is titled "Dietary exposures" and shows a list of settings, all of which are marked with a green checkmark. The settings are grouped into "Scope" and "Inputs". The "Relative potency factors" setting in the "Inputs" group is circled in green. A "Save Changes" button is visible at the bottom right of the settings area.

Category	Setting	Status
Scope	(optional) Populations (15 in scope)	✓
	Foods (3278 in scope) Processing types (32 in scope)	✓
	Substances (144 in scope)	✓
	Effects (1 in scope)	✓
Inputs	Consumptions per food as measured	✓
	Concentration models	✓
	Processing factors	✓
	Active substances (optional)	✓
	Relative potency factors	✓

Impute missing hazard data

1. Go to Hazard Characterizations

The screenshot shows the EuroMix software interface. The top navigation bar includes "MCRA 9 - EuroMix toolbox / Exposure, Hazard & Risk Assessment", "Dietary exposure t... / workspace", and "Dietary exposures / action". The user is logged in as "EuroMix03". The main content area is titled "Dietary exposures / Relative potency factors" and shows three sections: "Scope" (Substances: 144 in scope, Effects: 1 in scope), "Inputs" (Hazard characterisations), and "Relative potency factors" (Use data, Compute). The "Hazard characterisations" item in the Inputs section is circled in red.

Impute missing hazard data

1. Scroll down to the Hazard characterisations settings
2. Select "Impute missing target hazard data", and make sure the Munro P5 (unbiased for uncertainty) is selected.
3. We have now told the software to use (TTC based) imputed hazard doses for those substances that do not have a Point of Departure in the datafile.

Dietary exposures / Relative potency factors / Hazard characterisations

773e16f1 ▶

Hazard characterisations settings

Save Changes

Exposure type

Chronic

Target dose level

External

Include dietary and non-dietary routes of exposure

Target hazard dose type

Same as reference substance

Use BMDs from dose response models in preference to hazard doses (e.g. NOAELs)

Impute missing target hazard doses

Hazard dose imputation method

Munro P5 (unbiased for uncertainty runs)

Impute missing hazard data

1. Make sure to Save Changes

Dietary exposures / Relative potency factors / Hazard characterisations 773e16f1 ▶

Inter-species conversions (optional)

Intra species factors (optional)

Kinetic models (optional)

Hazard characterisations settings

Exposure type
Chronic ▼ i

Target dose level
External ▼ i

Include dietary and non-dietary routes of exposure i

Target hazard dose type
Same as reference substance ▼ i

Use BMDs from dose response models in preference to hazard doses (e.g. NOAELs) i

Impute missing target hazard doses i

Hazard dose imputation method
Munro P5 (unbiased for uncertainty runs) ▼ i

Save Changes

Summary overview

1. In the summary overview, check the scope, settings and data in the assessment (scroll down)
2. Run the simulation

Summary

General

Name	Dietary exposures training
Description	<i>no description</i>
Tags	<i>no tags</i>

Scope

Effects	Secondary input data exposure.mdb	v1
Foods	Secondary input data exposure.mdb	v1
Populations	Secondary input data exposure.mdb	v1
Substances	Secondary input data exposure.mdb	v1

Settings

Exposure type	Chronic
Dietary exposure calculation tier	EFSA Guidance Optimistic
Apply processing factors	Yes

Run the simulation

1. After you start running the simulation, you see a screen with waiting for activation. This takes 10-20 seconds
2. Then waiting for activation changes into running (second screenshot)
3. This might take 2-3 minutes for this exercise. If it takes longer than 10 minutes abort the job

The image shows two screenshots of a web interface for "Dietary exposures training".

The top screenshot shows a table with the following data:

Output	Status	Message	Date	Running time
<input type="checkbox"/> Dietary exposures training	Waiting for activation	Job scheduled for execution (waiting for available resources)...	-	-

The bottom screenshot shows the same table with the following data:

Output	Status	Message	Date	Running time
<input type="checkbox"/> Dietary exposures training	Running	Conversion finished	-	-

View the output

1. Click on the name of the calculation, optionally rename it first (i.e. to "Dietary exposures with imputed (TTC) values") to distinguish the run from the first one.
2. Go to dietary sub-action results
3. Look at the target hazard doses.

Scroll down and look at the available hazard sources and see the differences

View the output

1. Scroll down and look at the available hazard sources table with the potency origins and see the differences

Model code	Effect name	Effect code	Substance name	Substance code	Hazard characterisation (µg/kg bw)	Potency origin
-	Steatosis-liver	Steatosis-liver	1-methylcyclopropene	RF-0005-001-PPP	2	Imputed
-	Steatosis-liver	Steatosis-liver	1-naphthylacetamide	RF-0006-001-PPP	2	Imputed
-	Steatosis-liver	Steatosis-liver	1-naphthylacetic acid	RF-0007-001-PPP	2	Imputed
-	Steatosis-liver	Steatosis-liver	Abamectin (RD)	RF-0011-001-PPP	2	Imputed
-	Steatosis-liver	Steatosis-liver	Acequinocyl	RF-0013-001-PPP	2	Imputed
-	Steatosis-liver	Steatosis-liver	Acetamiprid	RF-0014-001-PPP	2	Imputed
-	Steatosis-liver	Steatosis-liver	Amisulbrom	RF-0470-001-PPP	2	Imputed
-	Steatosis-liver	Steatosis-liver	Amitrole	RF-0025-001-PPP	2	Imputed
-	Steatosis-liver	Steatosis-liver	Azadirachtin	RF-0030-001-PPP	2	Imputed
-	Steatosis-liver	Steatosis-liver	Benalaxyl (RD)	RF-0038-001-PPP	2	Imputed
-	Steatosis-liver	Steatosis-liver	Benfluralin	RF-0039-001-PPP	2	Imputed
-	Steatosis-liver	Steatosis-liver	Bensulfuron	RF-0493-001-PPP	2	Imputed
-	Steatosis-liver	Steatosis-liver	Bentazone (RD)	RF-0042-001-PPP	2	Imputed
-	Steatosis-liver	Steatosis-liver	Benthiavalicarb (RD)	RF-0043-001-PPP	2	Imputed
-	Steatosis-liver	Steatosis-liver	Bifenazate (sum of bifenazate plus bifenazate-diazene expressed as bifenazate)	RF-00003033-PAR	2	Imputed
-	Steatosis-liver	Steatosis-liver	Bitertanol	RF-0048-001-PPP	2	Imputed
-	Steatosis-liver	Steatosis-liver	Bixafen	RF-1056-001-PPP	2	Imputed
-	Steatosis-liver	Steatosis-liver	Bromopropylate	RF-0052-001-PPP	2	Imputed
-	Steatosis-liver	Steatosis-liver	Bromoxynil	RF-0053-002-PPP	2	Imputed

View the output

1. Go to dietary exposure
2. Open observed individual means
3. Open percentiles
4. Look at the Margin of Exposure at different percentile

MCRA 9 - EuroMix toolbox / Dietary exposure T... / Dietary exposures

Results / Dietary exposures with imputed (TTC) values

Sub-action results: **Dietary exposures**

- > Exposures by substance
- > Exposures by food and substance
- Observed individual means**
- > Graph total
- > Graph upper tail
- Percentiles**

Reference: Fluconazole, PoD = 530 µg/kg bw/day
Mean exposure: 0,82 (µg/kg bw/day)

Percentage	Exposure (µg/kg bw/day)	Percentage of PoD (%)	Nominal margin of exposure
50.00	0.6057	0.11	875
90.00	1.808	0.34	293.1
95.00	2.335	0.44	227
99.00	3.965	0.75	133.7
99.90	8.349	1.58	63.48
99.99	12.01	2.27	44.11

Results overview

Calculation method	Margin of Exposure		
	EFSA pessimistic	EFSA optimistic	TTC imputation EFSA optimistic
substances in scope (CAG)	144	144	144
number of imputations	0	0	99
Percentile			
50	51.09	4242	875
90	21.05	681.5	293.1
95	17.12	487.5	227
99	11.54	277	133.7
99.9	6.202	173.3	63.48
99.99	5.315	119.8	44.11

All examples are illustrations of how the data from the EuroMix test strategy can be used in future mixture risk assessment. The exercises should not be seen as a real risk assessment.

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EuroMix participants

22 beneficiaries from 16 countries linked to international organisations including WHO, FAO and EFSA.
EuroMix is coordinated by RIVM.

